

GREAT MASTER OF TURKISH POETRY

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Abstract

Yunus Emre (1240-1320), who has a large "Divan" with a magical structure of words, consisting of stanzas, couplets, tajnis and quatrains, and a 362-verse masnavi called "Admonition", is a great master of poetry in the history of the literature of Turkic-speaking peoples.

The history of the written Turkish literary and artistic language has been on a wide development path since the 13th century with the creativity of Mevlana Jalaladdin Rumi, his son the poet Sultan Valad, and Yunus Emre, who wrote with the motto "a few words are the property of the land, many words are the burden of animals".

However, we must not forget the fact that Maulana Jalaluddin, who is considered the "prophet of love", and his son Sultan Valad wrote in Persian. Therefore, in the same century, Hasanoglu in Azerbaijan and Yunus Emre in Anatolia are considered the first professional creators of poetry examples written in their mother tongue. As can be seen from the pearls of words as elegant, harmonious and instructive as the examples of poetry in "Dade Gorgud", Yunus Emre wrote in such a simple and clear, sweet, instructive and bright language that his poems for the reader of a Turkic-speaking nation, it is as native as a mother's breath, pure and dear as a mother's breast.

That is why, for almost 800 years, Yunus Emre's poetry has preserved its existence as an impregnable, indestructible fortress of poetic words. The genius poet conquered hearts with his poetry and art, and the poet's belief that "there is no mountain higher than the heart" has been proven true by the trials of history.

Yunus Emre's love of life seems to have been fertilized by the genius of Nizami Ganjavi and Jalaladdin Rumi, and at the same time, he was the first example, the first resource, the first fountain of vitality in the path of inspired creativity of the wordsmiths who came after him, such as Nasimi, Khatai, Fuzuli, Karacaoglu, Ashiq Veysel, Ashiq Alasgar.

Keywords: Yunus Emre, history of poetic, literary and artistic language.

Yunus Emre considers the human love of life as an invincible force that keeps the world and the universe in order, he calls his sofa "the book of love" and says that "love is a fiery object that confuses minds and excites the seas."

Taking into account the address in the Gakh district of Azerbaijan, the existence of the tomb of an art conqueror in ten places clearly shows that Yunus Amre is the memory of the people as a whole, and his poetry is the memory of the native language.

Yunus Amre is the first prominent creator of old Anatolian Turkish in the second half of the 13th century and the first half of the 14th century. F.K. Timurtaş wrote about this: "The Turkish nation found its own language and spirituality in the poetry of Yunus".[3, 8]

His book of poems called "Guldaste" opens with "Minajati Muhammad". In the eyes of Yunus Amra, Muhammad is the lord of the prophets, the pillar of religion... Sharia is the style of truth.

The poet considers God and his most enlightened servant Muhammad as the qibla of goodness, kindness, mercy and hope in the path of truth, and emphasizes that he is just and fair. Muhammad's greatness in mercy is described in the poem "God's Answer" with the verses "I will ask for the Ummah from me, I will not set your Ummah on fire, I will not make you angry, I will not leave you alone, I will forgive your Ummah", and the poet's astonishment and infinite joy in front of this greatness is described with the applause of "our sultan of a hundred thousand thanks".[1, 97]

With this belief, Yunus Amra unites the created and the created, equates the light of Muhammad in the human heart with the Sun, and stands at the same stage

as Hallaj Mansur, Fazlulla Naimi and Imaduddin Nasimi on the path of spreading Sufi teachings based on three levels: Sharia, sect and truth. He tries to spread this teaching not only in Anatolia, but also in all Asian countries.

In the poetry of Yunus, there is the integrity of the world, man and thought, there is a natural unity of a person's scientific, artistic, socio-philosophical, ethical, aesthetic and religious worldview, universal perfection and completeness of style. In his lyrics, people's life, customs and traditions, taste and psychology, belief in God, personal freedom, holy personalities, places and books in the history of Islamic religion, physical and spiritual beauty, universal feelings and thoughts are emblazoned with bright artistic colors.

Yunus Amre's poem is the most accurate mirror of the Turkish style of poetic expression and perfect artistic creativity. In him, the love of God and the love of the world flow like Oman.

Yunus Amre is a powerful wordsmith of his time, and he has his own poetic ideas and individual style concept about artistic creativity.

Jonah's poetry is a very instructive textbook of life, a source of moral advice. Unique literary personalities and masters of figurative words like Yunus Emre rarely grow up in life, they are born once in a hundred years. Because he understood this truth, he spoke about it in his poem. [1, 83]

Everyone who reads "Guldaste" as a researcher, purposefully and carefully, comes to the conclusion that Yunus Amre's poem is the greatness of the spirit of humanity in the history of Turkish language literature, the golden ratio of the art, which is more characteristic

for the weight of the syllables, the legal measure and order, the smooth flow of thoughts, the precise words.

It is the pinnacle of poetry that can be seen from all over the world with its structure, language richness and poetic fluency, wisdom and instructive capacity.

Yunus Amre is such a peak that neither the Moon sets nor the Sun goes out. That's why I don't want to say that he is immortal because of his love, "If I'm in love, I won't die anymore!" has a great moral right to say.

Thus, Yunus Emre illuminated the development path of Turkish-language folk poetry like the Sun and distributed gifts to Turkic-speaking villages in a large area from Anatolia to the Yenisei, from the Indian Ocean to the Balkan Peninsula, from the Carpathians to the Altai-Tian-Shan mountains. [1, 24]

Yunus Emre's poetry is easily absorbed by everyone, like pure mountain air, in a way that fully corresponds to the law of identity of the human thinking, especially the thinking of the Turkic peoples.

Everyone likes the native mother's lullaby, as if it calls the whole Islamic world to unity and unanimity.

There is such an example: "If there are five fingers, it is difficult to break them." The fingers on the hand are nothing individually, but when they are united,

they become a powerful fist." Therefore, Yunus Amre's poetry retains its ideological and artistic value even today.

In the following verses of the poet Mammad Aslan, who stands out for his creativity, language clarity and laconicity, poetic thought fluency, wisdom and instructiveness, the master of powerful words, who "holds the burden of poetry from the heart" like Yunus Amre, the hearts of poetry and art lovers are read and their infinite love is expressed.

Hello, old Yunus,
Hello, word fountain of the East!
Because of that face of hundreds of years
The voice of the Turk! [2, 113]

References

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